

RLS-Adapted Polynomial for Nonlinear Acoustic Echo Cancelling

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ABSTRACT

Low-cost audio components in hands-free telephone applications call for nonlinear adaptive echo cancellation. It has been demonstrated that a cascade of a polynomial and an FIR filter can cancel echoes due to nonlinearities of typical low-cost applications [1]. Overcoming the slow convergence of an NLMS-based adaptation [5], we derive an RLS-type adaptation for the polynomial preprocessor. Furthermore, we present a robust control of the RLS algorithm. Experiments with double-talk scenarios and real audio hardware show more than 8 dB overall echo reduction gain and fast and robust convergence of the polynomial. In addition, an implementation with reduced computational complexity and similar robustness is presented.

1 Introduction

With declining prices for DSP hardware, cheap audio components are becoming interesting for hands-free communication terminals leading to a nonlinear distortion of the reproduced speech signal. Another cause of nonlinearities is low battery voltage in mobile applications, which may overload the amplifier at the loudspeaker. As in speech signals only a high level of nonlinear distortion is audible, the near-end user will generally tolerate this. However, echo components due to nonlinearities cannot be compensated by the commonly used linear acoustic echo canceller (AEC). Therefore the far-end user may hear an annoying distorted echo of high volume speech portions, while the echo of low volume portions is removed by the linear canceller.

If the classical adaptive FIR filter is equipped with a polynomial preprocessing, the nonlinear echo can be greatly reduced, once the polynomial is of order 7 or higher [1]. This assumes the nonlinearities to be memoryless, which is a reasonable model for an overloaded amplifier. As the polynomial in [1] is not adaptive, and the NLMS adaptation proposed in [5] exhibits very slow convergence for 7th order polynomials, a fast and robust adaptation scheme for the preprocessor is desirable.

Other approaches aim at cancelling echoes originating from an echo path with dynamic nonlinearity [2, 3, 4]. They are applicable in high-quality communication systems, where relatively small nonlinearities occur due to electro-mechanic properties of the loudspeaker rather than saturation effects. They imply a high computational complexity [2], the need for an extra reference microphone [3], or suffer from convergence problems [4].

In Section 2 the cascade of an adaptive polynomial and an FIR filter, as introduced in [5], is revisited. Based on that a robust RLS adaptation for the preprocessor is developed in Section 3 and a complexity reduction through subsampled adaptation is proposed. The performance of both the fully sampled and the subsampled adaptation under realistic conditions is experimentally verified in Section 4.

2 Cascaded system

Fig. 1 shows a nonlinear acoustic echo canceller with cascaded adaptive filters. In [5] the joint NLMS adaptation of both stages was derived, based only on the final error signal $e[k]$. The output of the polynomial preprocessor

Figure 1: Nonlinear AEC with adaptive polynomial preprocessing

is

$$\hat{s}[k] = \mathbf{x}_p[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k] \quad (1)$$

with

$$\mathbf{x}_p[k] = [x[k], x^2[k], \dots, x^P[k]]^T, \quad (2)$$

and the coefficient vector

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k] = [\hat{a}_1[k], \dots, \hat{a}_P[k]]^T. \quad (3)$$

If $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$ is only slowly time-varying relative to the duration of the impulse response $\hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$, the output of the adaptive filter can be approximated by

$$\hat{y}[k] = \hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]^T \mathbf{X}_p[k] \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k] \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{X}_p[k] = [\mathbf{x}_p[k], \mathbf{x}_p[k-1], \dots, \mathbf{x}_p[k-N+1]]^T. \quad (5)$$

With this assumption, a gradient-type adaptation for both $\hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$ and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$ can be derived [4, 5]. The NLMS adaptation of the FIR filter $\hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$ is given in step 11 of Table 1, where α_h denotes the adaptation stepsize. The RLS adaptation of the preprocessor coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$ is derived in the next section.

3 Adaptation of the polynomial nonlinearity

As a starting point, the least squares (LS) determination of a time-invariant coefficient set $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ described in [1] is reviewed in Section 3.1. From this a recursive coefficient update is derived in Section 3.2. As the control of the adaptation speed is an important issue in AEC [6], a control mechanism for the RLS adaptation of the preprocessor as well as for the NLMS adaptation of the FIR filter is discussed in Section 3.3. Finally, in Section 3.4, the computational cost of the new algorithm is determined and an effective way of complexity reduction is proposed.

3.1 LS approach based on final error $e[k]$

In [1] the polynomial coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ are determined by a least squares (LS) fitting to a recorded training sequence. This sequence is obtained by passing a large number of audio samples $x[0] \dots x[k_0]$ through the loudspeaker-room-microphone system and recording the according microphone signal $d[0] \dots d[k_0]$ at the same time. With

$$\mathbf{u}[k] = \mathbf{X}_p[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{h}}[k], \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{U}[k_0] = [\mathbf{u}[0], \mathbf{u}[1], \dots, \mathbf{u}[k_0]]^T \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{d}[k_0] = [d[0], d[1], \dots, d[k_0]]^T \quad (8)$$

the LS problem for the coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ reads

$$\|\mathbf{U}[k_0] \hat{\mathbf{a}} - \mathbf{d}[k_0]\|_2^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{k_0} e^2[k] \rightarrow \min, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{U}[k_0]$ is a $(k_0 + 1) \times P$ matrix, e.g., a 10000×7 matrix in [1], and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ is determined via the pseudo-inverse

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \underbrace{(\mathbf{U}[k_0]^T \mathbf{U}[k_0])^{-1}}_{\mathbf{P}[k_0]} \underbrace{\mathbf{U}[k_0]^T \mathbf{d}[k_0]}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}[k_0]}. \quad (10)$$

3.2 RLS adaptation of preprocessor

The RLS (recursive least squares) algorithm [7] calculates $\mathbf{P}[k]$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}[k]$ of (10) recursively avoiding the inversion of $\mathbf{U}[k]^T \mathbf{U}[k]$. Furthermore, the LS estimation is equipped with a leaky memory, i.e. $\sum_{\kappa=0}^k \lambda^{\kappa-k} e^2[\kappa]$ is minimized instead of (9), so that time-varying systems can be tracked as well. The forgetting factor λ typically lies between 0.9 and 1. To avoid numerical instabilities, $\mathbf{P}[k]$ is periodically re-initialized with $\mathbf{I} \cdot \delta^{-1}$, where δ is a small positive constant and $\mathbf{I}$ is the $P \times P$ unity matrix. The joint adaptation of both stages is summarized

Table 1: Joint adaptation of FIR filter and polynomial

1.	$\hat{s}[k] = \mathbf{x}_p[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$
2.	$\hat{\mathbf{s}}[k] = [\hat{s}[k], \hat{s}[k-1], \dots, \hat{s}[k-N+1]]^T$
3.	$\mathbf{u}[k] = \mathbf{X}_p[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$
4.	$e_{\text{pri}}[k] = d[k] - \mathbf{u}[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$
5.	adaptation control (α_h, λ)
6.	$\mathbf{v}[k] = \lambda^{-1} \mathbf{P}[k] \mathbf{u}[k]$
7.	$\mathbf{g}[k] = \frac{\mathbf{v}[k]}{1 + \mathbf{u}[k]^T \mathbf{v}[k]}$
8.	$\mathbf{P}[k] = \lambda^{-1} \mathbf{P}[k] - \mathbf{g}[k] \mathbf{v}[k]^T$
9.	$\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k+1] = \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k] + \mathbf{g}[k] e_{\text{pri}}[k]$
10.	$e_{\text{post}}[k] = \mathbf{u}[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{a}}[k+1]$
11.	$\hat{\mathbf{h}}[k+1] = \hat{\mathbf{h}}[k] + \frac{\alpha_h}{\ \mathbf{s}[k]\ _2^2} \mathbf{s}[k] e_{\text{post}}[k]$

in Table 1, where the RLS algorithm for the adaptation of $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$ is contained in steps 6-10¹.

3.3 Control mechanism for the RLS adaptation

A major problem in AEC is the control of the adaptation stepsize to prevent divergence during double-talk and to allow fast adaptation after room variations. Many stepsize control methods for linear NLMS-adapted AECs provide an approximation to a stepsize, which is optimal with respect to the mean square FIR filter misalignment. It is based on an estimate of the filter misalignment and several signal powers [6] and is denoted by $\alpha_{\text{opt}}[k]$ ($0 \leq \alpha_{\text{opt}}[k] \leq 1$) here. If the residual echo $\varepsilon[k]$ contains nonlinear components, this concept must be extended, as nonlinear echo components disturb the adaptation of $\hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$ and linear echo components disturb the adaptation of $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$. Therefore the FIR filter stepsize α_h should be lowered at amplitude peaks of $x[k]$, and the preprocessor stepsize has to be chosen carefully, as described in [5].

¹Note that in contrast to the nomenclature in [7] the time index k is increased by one, so that a joint adaptation scheme can be formulated.

Using the RLS algorithm we have to control the forgetting factor λ in such a way that system changes can be tracked, which requires it to be rather small, i.e. λ well below 1. During double-talk or when the excitation $x[k]$ is low, λ should be near 1 to increase robustness. Therefore, we propose to control the forgetting factor depending on $\alpha_{\text{opt}}[k]$ as follows

$$\lambda[k] = 1 - \alpha_{\text{opt}}[k](1 - \lambda_{\text{min}}), \quad (11)$$

where λ_{min} represents the minimum forgetting factor. In conjunction with re-initialization of $\mathbf{P}[k]$ every 1000 steps using $\delta = 0.01$, the value $\lambda_{\text{min}} = 0.995$ shows robust operation in AEC environments in our experiments. For additional stabilization in situations with low excitation $x[k]$, the adaptation of $\hat{\mathbf{a}}[k]$ (step 9 in Table 1) is skipped, if the short-time peak amplitude of the input

$$\bar{x}[k] = \begin{cases} |x[k]| & |x[k]| \geq \bar{x}[k-1] \\ 0.99\bar{x}[k-1] + 0.01|x[k]| & |x[k]| < \bar{x}[k-1] \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

is below a certain threshold $\Theta = c \cdot \max\{|x[k]|\}$, where the choice of $c \in [0.2; 0.4]$ is not critical.

3.4 Computational complexity

A fast implementation of the RLS algorithm (see, eg. [7]) is not possible, as it would require $\mathbf{u}[k]$ to have a transversal structure. However, for practically relevant orders like $P = 7$ the RLS adaptation (step 6-10 in Table 1) costs only $2P^2 + 3P = 119$ multiplications (MUL) per sample. This is negligible compared to the NLMS-adapted linear filter, which costs $2N$ MUL/sample with N ranging from several hundred to more than one thousand, depending on the application.

The bottleneck is step 3 in Table 1, which costs $P \cdot N$ MUL/sample and which is required for either NLMS or RLS adaptation of the prefilter. This means that the proposed system with $P = 7$ costs about $9N$ MUL/sample, which is illustrated by the uppermost curve in Fig. 2. As the polynomial evaluation (step 1 in Table 1), which is required at every time step, is inexpensive, the complexity can be greatly reduced by subsampled adaptation, i.e. executing steps 3, 4, and 6-10 in Table 1 only every M -th step. During the other $M - 1$ steps the error is calculated by $e_{\text{post}}[k] = \hat{\mathbf{s}}[k]^T \hat{\mathbf{h}}[k]$, which costs only N MUL/sample instead of $NP + 2P^2 + 4P$.

In Fig. 2 the resulting multiplication effort is plotted over N for $M = 1, 2, 3, 4$. For comparison, the complexity of an NLMS-adapted linear AEC is shown as well. E.g., with $M = 4$, a nonlinear preprocessor with $P = 7$ only doubles the computational cost compared to a conventional linear AEC. Furthermore, experiments have shown that restricting the polynomial only to odd powers of $x[k]$ does not have a significant impact on the performance, which opens another way of saving complexity.

Figure 2: Multiplication effort for nonlinear AEC with seventh order RLS-adapted polynomial

The memory requirement of the nonlinear AEC is $2N + 3P + P^2 + NP$, the major part of which is the storage of $\mathbf{X}_p[k]$. If instead only the last N samples of $x[k]$ are stored, and the required powers are recalculated each adaptation step consuming extra NP/M MUL/sample, $N(P - 1)$ memory words can be saved.

4 Experiments

Using speech excitation and recordings from a real echo path, the adaptive nonlinear AEC is compared to a conventional linear one with respect to the echo return loss enhancement $\text{ERLE} = \mathcal{E}\{(d[k] - n[k])^2\} / \mathcal{E}\{(e[k] - n[k])^2\}$, where the local signal component $n[k]$ is subtracted for transparency. Section 4.1 examines whether the RLS-adapted polynomial preprocessing is an appropriate approach to the nonlinear echo problem with an overloaded amplifier. Then, in Section 4.2 the robustness of the adaptation is tested with an adverse double-talk scenario. With all simulations, the FIR filter length is $N = 250$ taps, which would suffice to achieve more than 25 dB ERLE if linear audio hardware was used in the same room.

4.1 Appropriateness and convergence of polynomial model

To verify that a memoryless polynomial can model real nonlinearities, the echo from a small loudspeaker (0.1 Watts) with an overloaded amplifier (1 Watt) in a room with short reverberation time ($T_{60} = 50$ ms) is recorded and no local signal is added. The amplitude of the loudspeaker signal $x[k]$ (see Fig. 3) has been chosen such that the nonlinear distortions at the loudspeaker are just audible but not annoying. A comparison between a linear AEC and the new nonlinear AEC with $P = 7$ is shown in Fig. 3. The polynomial is either determined offline by LS fitting as described in Section 3.1 (dashed curve) or adapted with the RLS algorithm of Sections 3.2 and 3.3 (upper solid curve). The results with both nonlinear systems emphasize that the polynomial model is appropriate, if an ERLE of about 25 dB is enough for the application in mind. Interestingly, the adaptive system even outperforms the fixed one, although the latter had access to the complete excitation sequence $x[0, \dots, k_0]$ and microphone sequence $d[0, \dots, k_0]$ in advance. This

Figure 3: Linear versus nonlinear AEC with precalculated and RLS-adapted polynomial preprocessing.

can be explained through the ability of the adaptive system to exploit the short-time statistics of the instationary excitation. Note that the RLS-adaptation exhibits very fast convergence.

4.2 Robustness under adverse conditions

Fig. 4 shows an adverse test scenario: while the far-end speech $x[k]$ has negligible background noise (and therefore also its echo $y[k]$), the local speech $n[k]$ contains clearly audible stationary background noise at -20 dB compared to its active speech level [8]. For an AEC this is a worst-case situation, as it has to cope with local distortion at all times, whereas the excitation $x[k]$ exhibits very low power at some times. Using a simpli-

Figure 4: Fully sampled and subsampled adaptation of $\hat{a}[k]$ versus linear AEC.

fied stepsize control with explicit access to $n[k]$ supplying a coarse estimate of $\alpha_{opt}[k]$, a conventional linear AEC is compared to an AEC with adaptive polynomial of order $P = 7$ both with fully sampled and subsampled ($M = 4$) adaptation. The experiment has been performed with the real system and the excitation $x[k]$ described in the last section. The results are shown in Fig. 4, where the dashed curve represents the subsampled adaptation. The ERLE curves show robust behaviour of the nonlinear AEC under these adverse con-

ditions: even with subsampled adaptation, the nonlinear canceller outperforms the linear one at nearly all times. About 8 dB ERLE is gained compared to the linear AEC at loud speech portions. The performance loss due to four-fold subsampling of the preprocessor adaptation is only about 1...3 dB ERLE. This allows the conclusion that even with subsampled adaptation the proposed nonlinear AEC adapts robustly in realistic communication situations.

5 Summary

A nonlinear AEC with polynomial preprocessing has been investigated. To achieve fast convergence of the polynomial coefficients, an RLS-type adaptation was developed. A new control method for the RLS algorithm's forgetting factor allows robust operation under the adverse conditions encountered in AEC, and improves the echo reduction of a classical linear AEC by up to 8 dB when operating with real audio hardware. The relatively high computational cost can be reduced by subsampled prefilter adaptation, as the prefilter converges very fast.

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